

Cerebral Vasculature and Disease Pathology of Ischemic Stroke and Role of Phytochemicals in Ischemic Stroke Therapy

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Abstract

Cerebral ischemic stroke is considered as an improper supply of oxygen due to the altered homeostatic mechanisms in the cerebral blood vessels. Brain cells have high metabolic rate and so are sensitive to oxygen deprivation. Nutrient rich blood in brain is supplied by arterial circulation and the used blood drains out by venous circulation which is together referred as “cerebral circulation” whereas the restricted blood flow initiates several abnormalities in blood vessels which together contribute to hypoxic-ischemic insult. CNS components however have the capacity to withstand this insult for a limited time period known as “hypoxic-ischemic tolerance” where other molecular phenomenon progresses the disease. The region that is surmised to die within few minutes of such an ischemic event is considered as “ischemic core” and the region that extends between the core and the area of normal perfusion is considered as “ischemic penumbra”. Chronic ischemic insult is irreversible but acute ischemic insult is reversible by two approaches namely reperfusion of the vascular bed (vascular approach) as early as possible and intervening the ischemic cascade initiated neuronal damage (cellular approach). The pathophysiological events taking place in ischemic stroke are strictly time bound and sequential. Intervention of medicinal plants in cerebral ischemia has been targeting several strike factors like oxidative stress in reperfusion injury, hypoxia in penumbral sites, altered BBB permeability, infarctions and many other interrelated pathological manifestations. The complexity of stroke pathophysiology can be addressed by phytochemicals via one-drug-multitarget strategy by targeting molecular mechanisms like antioxidation, antiinflammation, neuroprotection etc. This article covers few of such potential phytochemicals offering exclusive protection against ischemic stroke.

Key Words: Cerebral ischemic stroke, cerebral circulation, hypoxic-ischemic tolerance, ischemic core, ischemic penumbra, medicinal plants, phytochemicals

INTRODUCTION

Stroke is a cerebrovascular disease (CVD) represented by anomalous blood flow to brain. According to WHO, stroke is a rapidly developing condition of clinical signs related to focal or global interruption in the cerebral function for which

symptoms last for 24 hours or longer or lead to death with neither of any apparent cause outside of the vascular origin (1). The vast majority of CVD deaths are due to stroke. It is diversified as ischemic stroke due to blood clots and hemorrhagic stroke due to bleeding of blood vessels. Cerebral ischemic stroke is considered as an improper supply of oxygen due to the altered homeostatic mechanisms in the cerebral blood vessels and they account for 80% of strokes in comparison with the hemorrhagic strokes. Under epidemiological considerations, ischemic stroke or infarction can be categorized into a) thrombotic cerebral infarction (caused by obstruction of artery with ischemia in all or part of the occluded territory), b) embolic cerebral infarction (caused by embolism of clot in cerebral arteries coming from other parts of the arterial system), and c) lacunar cerebral infarction (results from small and deep infarcts in the territory of minor penetrating arteries). The earliest global estimate from 1990 GBD study ranked cerebrovascular diseases as the second leading cause of death (2) while it also stands as a major cause of disability with significantly increased burden (3). According to CDC, cerebrovascular disease stands as a 5th cause of death mortality. According to National Center for Health Statistics, out of 10 prominent causes of mortality, the age adjusted death rate due to stroke has been increased from 38.8 in 2020 to 41.1 in 2021 ($p < 0.05$) (4). The National Vital Statistics System- Mortality Data 2022, identifies cerebrovascular diseases as the 5th preeminent causes of death counting for 165,393 deaths in 2022 compared to 162,890 deaths in 2021 to 150,005 deaths in 2019 to 1,47,810 deaths in 2018 with 49.6 deaths per 100,000 (5). It also remains as a prominent cause of DALYs and majority of stroke DALYs are reported from developing countries. In countries like India, the cause patterns related to mortality were based on the mortality registration systems namely MCCD, for urban India, and ASCD for rural areas of India. It was forecasted that the cases of cerebral stroke in Indian senior citizens by 2050 would be 3.3 million (6). The duration of stroke, prevalence, access to medication, rehabilitation, and the severity of stroke are required to measure the relative risk of death as well as case fatality in stroke survivors. The community based surveys reviewed by meta-analysis during 1960-2018 revealed that disease burden of stroke is at great extent in India (7).

Brain with its structural and functional dynamism acts as a complicated machine with significantly potential cellular machinery including neuronal and non-neuronal cells (astrocytes, microglia, oligodendrocytes, and ependymal cells) (8). The functional demands of the brain are ministered by blood and this service is considered significant because brain cells compared to all other cells have higher metabolic rate and so are sensitive to oxygen deprivation. Brain in itself is an energy-intensive organ by demanding almost 50 % of the body glucose (9). Nutrient rich blood is supplied by arterial circulation and the used blood drains out by venous circulation which is together referred as “cerebral circulation”. The arterial circulation based on anatomical positioning of brain is branched into anterior cerebral and posterior cerebral circulations. Likewise, based on the size and content it is branched into macrocirculation and microcirculation (10). Blood from heart’s aortic arch travels through the carotid arteries of either side so as to supply brain. Further, four arteries supply blood to brain namely two internal carotids + two vertebral arteries. Internal carotid arteries along with external carotid arteries are the branches of common carotid artery on either sides. These internal carotid arteries propose anterior circulation whereas vertebral arteries

propose posterior circulation (11). These circulations connect to each other by forming a ring called “circle of Willis” which combats the altered hemodynamics of brain and thereby protects the cerebral artery and blood brain barrier (12). The arterial cerebral circulation is maintained by several factors like level of metabolism, quantity of blood supply (hyperemia or excess supply, ischemia or deficient supply), viscosity and pH of the blood, autoregulation (regulation of the vessel diameter accordingly), intracranial pressure or ICP (pressure exerted by interstitial fluids inside the cranium), cerebral perfusion pressure (pressure excluding ICP) and autonomic neurogenic control. Abnormal flow of this cerebrovascular blood to brain leads to cerebrovascular disease which is an indelible disability and a burning cause of death worldwide (13). The etiology differentiates cerebrovascular diseases into stroke (event due to interrupted blood supply), carotid stenosis (narrowing of carotid arteries), vertebral stenosis (narrowing of vertebral arteries), intracranial stenosis (narrowing of arteries within the skull), aneurysms (localised swellings in the arteries) and vascular malformations (abnormalities in the vessel development).

Cerebral stroke, technically called as encephalic vascular accident occurs due to inadequate blood flow to the tissue. This inadequacy is termed as “ischemia” which is accompanied by impaired oxygen supply named “hypoxia”. Generally, stroke is considered to be the fourth and fifth prominent cause of death in women and men respectively (14). There is an increased prevalence of CVD burden in younger adults (3). Hypoxia and ischemia initiate metabolic changes in brain cells and results in altered membrane lipid composition as well as enzyme activities at cellular level. The blood flow is restricted due to abnormalities in the blood vessels by means of stenosis (vessel narrowing), thrombosis (clot formation in the vessel), embolism (blockade due to unplugged thrombus travelling in the stream and getting clogged), and haemorrhage (bleeding due to rupture in the vessel). All these conditions contribute to the hypoxic-ischemic insult. CNS components however have the capacity to withstand this insult for a limited time period known as “hypoxic-ischemic tolerance” (15) where other molecular phenomenon progresses the disease. Primary prevention of the disease focuses on addressing the vascular risk factors while secondary prevention focus on the recurrence after stroke incidence (16). Despite of the advancements in the diagnosis and management, stroke stands as preeminent reason for death and disability.

Cerebral ischemia is considered to be the pathological condition with inadequate blood supply to the tissues in the different regions of brain. The site of ischemia includes two regions namely ischemic core region and ischemic penumbra region. The region that is surmised to die within few minutes of ischemic event is considered as “ischemic core” and the region that extends between the core and the area of normal perfusion is considered as “ischemic penumbra”. Penumbra is the region salvageable by reperfusion and other pharmacological interventions (17,18). However, uncontrolled reperfusion kills neurons raising an emergency where ROS production overrides the ROS disposal (19). Brain exhibits an extraordinary phenomenon of tolerating the ischemic insult than other organs depending on the density of insult, concentration of energy stores, and energy expenditure which further rely upon the temperature, functional activity and interference of other substances like drugs. The difference also lies within the vulnerability of different regions of the brain (20). The

pathophysiological processes involved in ischemia are excitotoxicity (21), oxidative stress (22,23), inflammation (24,25), apoptosis (26,27) and reperfusion injury (28). Each of these processes have a distinctive time frame and they overlap with each other so as to damage the cells with in the ischemic region namely neurons, glial cells and other endothelial cells (29). These pathophysiological mechanisms differentiate cerebral ischemia into three variants namely global ischemia, focal ischemia and microembolism. Global ischemia arises by complete cessation of blood flow after a carotid artery occlusion, cardiac arrest, strangulation, intracranial hypertension or severe shock, and causes either transient or permanent damage. Focal ischemia is manifested mostly by thrombotic MCAO or any other arterial occlusions resulting in either transient or permanent damage. Microembolism is featured by several fat microembolic plaques after bone fractures, cardiac surgeries etc (30).

Following ischemia, reperfusion injury clearly is a condition that ensembles deprivation chased by restoration of blood flow to that particular area that has undergone ischemia (28). In reperfusion injury, there occurs an excessive formation of free radicals both of oxygen and nitrogen and causes reoxygenation which contributes as a secondary consequence to ischemic injury (31). Appropriate post-conditioning of global cerebral ischemia/reperfusion induce injury facilitates cerebral outflow (32). Global ischemia is considered as a non-stroke ischemic condition resulting in scarce blood supply throughout the brain that merely effects CA1 region of the hippocampus and the cortex responsible for learning and memory function (33). Treatment strategies for cerebral ischemia involve a) mechanisms to facilitate cerebral blood flow by anti-platelet drug: intravenous tissue plasminogen activator induced thrombolysis (34) and anti-coagulant drugs, b) mechanisms to improve neuroprotection through free radical scavengers, cytokines, neurotropic factors induced gene therapy, and c) mechanisms that involve both intrinsic stem cell activation and extrinsic stem cell transplantation (35). Chronic ischemic insult is irreversible but acute ischemic insult is reversible by two approaches namely reperfusing the vascular bed (vascular approach) as early as possible and intervening the ischemic cascade initiated neuronal damage (cellular approach). Vascular approach proposes treatment strategies in terms of intravenous thrombolysis, ultrasound enhanced thrombolysis, intra-arterial thrombolysis, fibrinogen depleting drugs and endovascular interventions. At cellular level, neuroprotection proposes drugs by identifying the compromised tissue compartments in the neurotoxic cascade sooner so as to extend the therapeutic window in the penumbra which will benefit the rational therapy against acute cerebral ischemia (36).

The iatrogenic effects of the conventional medicine laid paths towards therapy by means of using natural medicine obtained from herbal plants. WHO has encouraged the employment of traditional plant medicine if the needs remain unmet by using modern systems whereas physicians dismiss them often as harmless placebos (37). Herbal medicines are also found effective when alloyed with allopathic medicines. Proper plant identification and their quality control based on the technological analysis (38) contributes to the generation of herbal medicines that are potential and efficient. Mechanism based screening (39) of phytochemicals is a potential outbreak to provide useful herbal medicine for certain uncompromising diseases and conditions. Rationally designed and carefully graded synergistic herbal products and formulations with advanced

scientific evidences will crash the new drug discovery strategies (40). Scientific approach of herbal medicines focuses on standard methods of evaluation for their safe and effective principles when compared to traditional medicine (41). Herbal medicines are technically categorized under complementary and alternative medicine with inevitable socio-demographic association (42). The principal components of the herbal medicine are their bioactive, non-nutrient components colloquially called as “phytochemicals” (43). The well extracted phytochemicals in today’s research are dominant players in functional foods (44). Phytochemicals based on their metabolic function are deciphered into primary and secondary metabolic components. When the primary metabolites are imperative for survival, secondary metabolites are distinguished with their abilities to protect against pathogens, UV mediated damage (45) *etc.* These secondary metabolites are generated from four different pathways named after their precursors a) Shikimic acid, b) Malonic acid, c) Mevalonic acid and d) Methylerythritol phosphate respectively (46). Based on their structure and functional group, the major categorical classes include terpenoids, polysaccharides, phenolics, sulphur containing phytoalexins, nitrogen containing alkaloids, flavonoids, and hydrocarbons (47) as elaborated in the Table 1.

Intervention of medicinal plants in cerebral ischemia has been targeting several strike factors like oxidative stress in reperfusion injury, hypoxia in penumbral sites, altered BBB permeability, infarctions and many other interrelated pathological manifestations. Pre-treatment with *Artemisia absinthium* extract decreased thiobarbituric acid reactive substances in focal cerebral ischemic reperfusion injury (48). Superoxide scavenging activity of *Canna indica* root extract was studied against cerebral ischemia reperfusion injury (49). *Camellia japonica* extract offered protection against ischemic/reperfusion injury by inhibiting lipid peroxidation and reducing blood-brain barrier permeability (50). Polyphenols of *Camellia sinensis* offered protection against elevated lipid peroxidation end products as well as eicosanoids in ischemic/reperfusion injury (51). Pre-conditioning with *Gastrodia elata* in ischemic models protected against excitotoxicity in global ischemic models (52) and offered antioxidant neuroprotection in focal cerebral ischemic models (53). *Ginkgo biloba* extract indicated inhibitory effect on nitric oxide formation after transient BCCAO (54). Neuroprotective benefits of *Lavandula officinalis* extract (55) as well as oil (56) in ischemic/reperfusion injury were assigned by antioxidant potential. Pre-treatment with the leaf extract of *Olea europaea* was protective against infarct volume, edema, BBB permeability as well as neurobehavioral deficits in stroke reperfusion models (57). The neuroprotective, anti-ischemic and anti-oxidant effects were offered by oleuropein (58). It also increased brain phosphatidylcholine levels and decreased ceramide levels as a means of neuroprotection (59). Neuroprotection by maintaining brain-water homeostasis in penumbral sites was observed in pre-treatment with dietary virgin olive oil (60). *Oscimum basilicum* extract rendered protection in transient global ischemia and reperfusion injury through elevated glutathione levels (61). *Osmium sanctum* extract pre-treatment upregulated superoxide dismutase activity and reduced malondialdehyde levels in bilateral common carotid artery occlusion/reperfusion model (62). Baicalin from *Scutellaria baicalensis* roots increased hippocampal BDNF expression in focal cerebral ischemia/ reperfusion injury (63). Extract of *Spatholobi caulis* was found to be effective against focal stroke/reperfusion by promoting BDNF levels (64).

Likewise, many plants extracts have been found beneficial to achieve protection against cerebral ischemic/reperfusion injury in stroke.

Phytochemicals are known to protect from ischemic damage through different modulating strategies associated with excitotoxicity, BBB permeability, inflammation, oxidative stress, cell component protection, cell death mechanisms etc (65). The pathophysiological events taking place in ischemic stroke are strictly time bound and sequential. For example, disrupted ionic balance and excitotoxicity are addressed within first few minutes of insult followed by oxidative damage that appears within hours peaking at reperfusion which is further indulged with inflammation lasting for days to weeks after reperfusion (66). In clinical practice, this pathology is managed by recanalization (with thrombolytics + management with antiplatelet drugs and anticoagulants) (67) and neuroprotection (from pathological factors with edaravone, n-butylphthalide) whereas neurogenesis is proposed for recovery. Several phytochemicals have been investigated for their protective functions in ischemic physiology. During the recent times, it is worthwhile to know that one-drug-multitarget strategy is beneficial to address the complexity in stroke physiology which in turn exists as an inherent property with phytochemicals (68). Natural products from plants are investigated as potential sources in stroke prophylaxis and management (69). It was reviewed that about 46 flavanoids, 7 stilbenoids, 20 phenolic compounds, 56 terpenoids, 19 alkaloids were investigated for their neuroprotective mechanisms (65). Flavanones in citrus fruits were observed to reduce the risk of stroke (70). Habitual flavonoid food intake was implied to reduced stroke incidence (71). Selected flavonoids proved to increase neuronal vitality, tissue perfusion, and blood flow as well as reduce ischemic-related apoptosis (72) and inflammation (73). Stilbene glycosides were known to improve stroke outcome by upregulating SIRT3 related pathways (74) and were known for their properties against inflammation (75). Pterostilbene by microglial modulation is known to alleviate ischemia-reperfusion injury (76,77). Resveratrol (78) and polydatin (79) were other important phytochemicals investigated against ischemic stroke. Phenolic derivatives reported multi-faceted properties (80) for neuroprotection while terpenoids achieved the same through PI3K/Akt signaling (81,82). Alkaloids like berberine, sinomenin, vinpocetin on the other hand produced effective properties against inflammation (83).

Phytochemicals are known to promote hormesis (84) and activate stress response mechanisms at safe lower doses (85). Phytochemicals activate Nrf-2/ARE-dependent free radical destructive pathways (86) to induce antioxidant enzyme systems (87). Phytochemicals are also known to enhance the expression of chaperons (heat shock proteins) (88), glucose-regulated proteins, and growth factors (89). Increased expression of proinflammatory cytokines like tumour necrosis factor in response to NF κ B switches by phytochemicals at low doses was effective against neuronal stress mechanisms (90) while in case of resident neuroimmune cells, this NF κ B signaling is known to be inhibited for their antiinflammatory responses (91). Neuronal dyshomeostasis of calcium and dysfunction of mitochondria (92) are known to be protected by phytochemicals via SIRT1/FOXO3 activation leading to neuronal survival (93). Phytochemicals activate downstream PPAR γ coactivator (PGC) - 1 alpha (PGC-1a) via AMPK signaling to control energy dynamics (94). Thrombosis in ischemic stroke in general is treated by anticoagulants (interfere with plaque expansion), antiplatelet

drugs (inhibit thrombus formation) and fibrinolytic agents (dissolve formed thrombus). Investigating specific phytochemicals from herbal sources possessing anti-thrombotic effects is an intriguing area of research while specific anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-apoptotic phytochemicals are proven to be successful at preclinical research level to combat ischemic stroke (95).

Oxygen deficit and glucose deprivation after occlusion to an artery during an acute ischemic insult upregulates the excitotoxic and proinflammatory gene expression while downregulating the intracellular protective gene expression. This can be altered by the provision of antioxidants that would not only increase the cell survival but stifle the inflammatory responses (96). Natural compounds promote antioxidation (97) and nutraceuticals act as potential prophylactic and therapeutic adjuvants against stroke (98). Phytochemicals readily address the molecular mechanisms in stroke by microglial/ macrophage activation (99). Polyphenols are known to be stroke preventive (100) and offer protection by TLR4 signaling (101). Flavanoids are evidenced to improve cerebral blood flow (102). Cocoa flavonoids by provoking angiogenesis and neurogenesis in the regions of learning and memory (103) improved neuroprotection while curcumin does it by improving differentiation of neural stem cells (104), resveratrol preserved the microstructures of memory and hippocampus (105). Omega-3 FAs challenged the cerebral environmental changes and protected brain cells (106). It is suggested that DHA optimizes synaptic homeostasis (107). Few of the potential phytochemicals that showed activity against ischemic stroke are listed in Table 2.

CONCLUSION:

Ischemic stroke is considered to be a debilitating disease well-known for its poor structural and functional outcomes worldwide. The conventional therapy limits complete recovery and contributes to long-lasting disability whereas mechanism based screening of phytochemicals provide potential benefit for uncompromising conditions like stroke. Several phytochemicals have been investigated for their abilities which interfere with pathological mechanisms of stroke. This review summarizes few of the phytochemicals that act through mechanisms like antioxidation, antiinflammation, antiapoptosis and BBB mediated neuroprotection thus proposing their considerable worth in clinical application to improve stroke management.

ABBREVIATIONS:

ASCD – Annual Survey of Cause of Death
BBB – Blood Brain Barrier
BCCAO – Bilateral Common Carotid Artery
BDNF – Brain Derived Neurotropic Factor
CA1 – Cornu Ammonis region 1
CDC – Center for Disease Control and Prevention
CNS – Central Nervous System
CVD – Cerebrovascular Disease
DALYs – Disability-adjusted Life Years
DHA – Docosahexaenoic acid
FAs – Fatty acids
FOXO3 – Forkhead box protein O
GBD – Global Burden of Diseases
ICP – Intracranial Pressure

MCAO – Middle Cerebral Artery Occlusion
MCCD – Medical Certification of Cause of Death
NF κ B – Nuclear factor kappa B
Nrf2/ARE – Nuclear factor erythroid 2–related factor 2/antioxidant response element
PI3K/Akt – Phosphoinositide -3-kinase/AK strain transforming
PPARGC1A – Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1 α
ROS – Reactive Oxygen Species
SIRT – Silent Mating Type Information Regulation
TLR – Toll-like receptor

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Table 1. List of Secondary Metabolites

Category	Types	Examples	Activities	References
Terpenes				
Hemiterpenes	-	Angelic acid, Isovaleric acid	Biofuels	108-110
Monoterpenes	Acyclic	Citral, Myrcene	Aroma and flavour	111
	Monocyclic	Menthol, Carvone		
	Bicyclic	α -Pinene, α -Thuzone		
Sesquiterpenes	Acyclic	Farnesol, Nerolidol	Anti-infective, antitumour and antiinflammatory	112
	Monocyclic	Humulene, α -Bisabolol		
	Bicyclic	Chamazulene		
	Tricyclic	Thujopsene		
Diterpenes	Linear	α -Tocopherol	Biopesticides	113
	Bicyclic	Oryzalexin		
	Tetracyclic	Momilactone A		
Triterpenes	Linear	Squalene	Anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidative, anti-viral, anti-bacterial and anti-fungal, immunomodulatory	114,115
	Bicyclic	α -Polypodatetraene		
	Tricyclic	Malabaricane		
	Tetracyclic	Cucurbitacin-I		
	Pentacyclic	Oleanane		
Tetraterpenes	-	β -Carotene, Lycopene, Lutein	Antidegenerative, antiatherosclerotic, antiinflammatory, immunomodulatory, antioxidant and anti-HIV	116
Polysaccharides				
Homopolysaccharides	Glucans	Cellulose, Starch	Anti-tumour, immunomodulatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, anticoagulant, antidiabetic, antiviral, and hypoglycemic	117
	Mannans	Konjac glucomannan		
Heteropolysaccharides		Agarose, Pectin		
Phenolics				
Simple	Phenolic	Eugenol	Antiinflammatory,	118

	phenylpropane		neuroprotective, antimicrobial, anticancer, antioxidant, cosmetic	
	Phenolic aldehyde	Vanillin		
	Phenolic acids	Salicylic acid, Ferulic acid, Caffeic acid, coumarins		
Tannins	Hydrolysed	Gallotannins, Ellagitannins	Antiviral, antibacterial, anti-tumour, antioxidant	119
	Condensed	Proanthocyanidins		
	Complex	Acutissimin		
Coumarins	Simple	Umbelliferone	Anticancer, antibacterial, antimalarial, anticoagulant, anti-inflammatory, casein kinase-2 (CK2) inhibitory, antifungal, antiviral, Alzheimer's disease inhibition, neuroprotective, anticonvulsant, phytoalexins, ulcerogenic, and antihypertensive	120,121
	Furanocoumarins	Psoralen, angelicin		
	Pyranocoumarins	Xanthylectin, seselin		
	Pyrone-substituted	Dicumarol		
Flavonoids	Isoflavones/ Phytoestrogens (B-ring linked to 3C of C-ring)	Genistin, Genistein, Diadzein	Antioxidative, anti-inflammatory, anti-carcinogenic and antimutagenic	122
	Neoflavonoids/ White flavonoids (B-ring linked to 4C of C-ring)	Dalbergin		
	Bioflavonoids (B-ring linked to 2C of C-ring)	Flavones (Apigenin, luteolin); Flavonols (Quercetin, rutin, myricetin, kaemferol); Chalcones (Arbutin, phloretin); Anthocyanins (Cyanidin, malvidin)		
Chromones and xanthonenes	Chromones	Eugenin, khellin	Antiviral, antimicrobial, anticancer, antiinflammatory,	123

			antioxidant	
	Xanthones	i) simple oxygenated; ii) non-oxygenated; iii) xanthonolignoids; iv) bisxanthones; v) prenylated and related xanthines; vi) miscellaneous xanthones	Antiinflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, cardiovascular protective, hepatoprotective and cytotoxic activities	124
Stilbenes	Stilbenes with hydroxyl substitution	Resveratrol, polydatin	Anticancer, antimicrobial, antioxidant, antidegenerative diseases, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, neuroprotective, anti-aging, and cardioprotective	125,126
	Stilbenes with methoxyl substitution	Pterostibene		
Lignans: Classical	Dibenzylbutanes	Niranthin, terameprocol, secoisolariciresinol	Anticancer, antiviral, antioxidants, and modulators of estrogen activity	127,128
	Dibenzylbutyrolactones	Arctigenin, yatein, hinokinin		
	Arylnaphthalenes	Diphyllin, podophyllotoxin		
	Substituted tetrahydrofurans	Lariciresinol, clemastatin B		
	Diaryl furofurans	Sesamin, phylligenin		
	Dibenzocyclooctenes	Bicyclol		
Lignans: Neolignans	1-4 Benzodioxane lignans	Silymarin		
	Secolignans	Piperomins A and B		
Sulphur containing phytoalexins				
Phytoanticipins	Glucosinolates	Myrosinase	Antioxidant, antiinflammatory, anti-infective, antitumor	129,130
	Thiosulfinates	Alliin, petivericin		
	Thiophenes	Ecliprostin		
	Polysulphanes			
Low molecular weight	-	Elemental sulphur,		

phytoalexins		Camalexin		
Alkaloids				
Tropane	-	Atropine, cocaine	Antiproliferative, antibacterial, antioxidant, anticancer, antimalarial, anesthetic, stimulant	131
Pyrrolizidine	-	Senecionine		
Piperidine	-	Piperine, lobeline		
Quinoline alkaloids	-	Quinine, quinidine, cinchonine		
Isoquinoline	-	Berberine, Papaverine		
Indole	-	Vincristine, reserpine, yohimbine		
Steroid	-	Latifolinin, solanocapsin		
Imidazole	-	Pilocarpine		
Purine	-	Caffeine, theophylline, theobromine		
Pyrrolidine	-	Hygrine, brevicolline		
Saponins				
Steroidal	-	Diosgenin	Expectorant, anti-inflammatory, vasoprotective and antimicrobial	132
Triterpenoid	-	Glycyrrhizin, soyasaponin I		
Lipids				
Fixed oils	-	Palmitic acid, oleic acid	Antiinflammatory, antiseptic, antioxidant, anti-aging	133-135
Waxes	-	Jojoba wax		
Essential oils	-	Lavender oil, peppermint oil		

Table 2. List of Phytochemicals with potential against ischemic stroke

S. No	Phytochemical	Category	Mechanism	Reference
1.	Apigenin	Flavone	BBB protection ; histone acetylation; antiinflammation	136-138
2.	Arjunolic acid	Triterpenoid	Antioxidation	139
3.	Astaxanthin	Tetraterpenoid	Neuroprotection; antioxidation and antiapoptosis;	140,141
4.	Baicalein	Flavone	Antiinflammation, antiapoptosis, antiautophagy	142,143
5.	Berberine	Alkaloid	Antiinflammation, antiapoptosis	144,145

6.	Borneol	Monoterpenoid	Enhanced neurovascular function, antiapoptosis; antiinflammation	146
7.	Capsaicin	Alkaloid	Antioxidation and antiinflammation; Antiexcitotoxicity; neurovascular protection	147-149
8.	Chrysin	Flavone	Antiinflammation; antioxidation	150
9.	Curcumin	Polyphenol	Antiautophagy; antiinflammation, antiapoptosis; neurogenesis, antioxidation, mitochondrial and BBB protection	151-153
10.	Daidzein	Isoflavone	Antioxidation	154
11.	Diammonium glycyrrhizinate	Triterpenoid	Antiapoptosis; antiinflammation	155,156
12.	Epigallocatechin-3-gallate	Flavanol	Antiapoptosis; antiexcitotoxicity; antiinflammation; antioxidation; BBB protection	157-161
13.	Eriodictyol	Flavanone	Antiinflammation	162
14.	Fisetin	Flavanol	Antiinflammation	163
15.	Fucoxanthin	Tetraterpenoid	Antioxidation	164
16.	Genistein	Isoflavone	Antioxidation and antiapoptosis; vascular protection	165,166
17.	Hesperidin	Flavanone	Antioxidation	167,168
18.	Hydroxysafflor yellow A	Chalcone	Neuroprotection; antiinflammation; antiapoptosis; enhanced neurotrophin release; mitochondrial function and biogenesis	169-173
19.	Icariin	Flavanol	Antioxidation, antiinflammation	174,175
20.	Kaempferol-3-O-rutinoside	Flavanol	Mitochondrial protection; Antiinflammation	176-178
21.	Luteolin	Flavone	Matrix metalloproteinase9 inhibition; antiinflammation, antioxidation, antiapoptosis	179,180
22.	Mulberroside A	Stilbenoid	Antiinflammation	181
23.	Myricetin	Flavanol	Antiapoptosis; autophagic restoration; antiinflammation and antioxidation	182-184
24.	Naringenin	Flavanone	Antiinflammation; antioxidation; antiapoptosis	185,186
25.	Naringin	Flavanone	Endoplasmic reticulum stress inhibition	187

26.	Nobiletin	Flavone	Neuroprotection and antiapoptosis; antiinflammation; antioxidation; reduced BBB permeability	188-190
27.	Oxymatrine	Alkaloid	Neurogenesis; neuroprotection	191,192
28.	Piperine	Alkaloid	Antiinflammation and antioxidation; neuroprotection;	193,194
29.	Polydatin	Stilbenoid	Neuroprotection; antiapoptosis; BBB protection, antiinflammation; antioxidation	195-197
30.	Pterostilbene	Stilbenoid	Antiinflammation; antioxidation, antiapoptosis	198,199
31.	Quercetin	Flavonol	Neuroprotection; increased energy metabolism; antioxidation, antiapoptosis	200-203
32.	Resveratrol	Stilbenoid	Cerebroprotection; calcium modulation; antiinflammation; extended ischemic tolerance; antioxidation, antiapoptosis, enhanced synaptic transmission efficiency; BBB protection	204-212
33.	Rosmarinic acid	Phenolic compound	Antioxidation; antiinflammation; synaptogenesis, BBB protection	213-217
34.	Rutin	Flavonol	Antiinflammation; Enhanced estrogen receptor activity; antioxidation	218-220
35.	Scutellarin	Flavone	Cerebral protection; antiexcitotoxicity; antioxidation and antiinflammation	221-223
36.	Silymarin	Flavanolignan	Antiinflammation	224
37.	Trigonelline	Alkaloid	Glutathione mediated antimyeloxygenase activity	225
38.	Ursolic acid	Triterpenoid	Antiinflammation; antioxidation	226,227
39.	Vinpocetine	Alkaloid	Antiinflammation	228
40.	Vitexin	Flavone	Antiautophagy; antiapoptosis;	229,230